

Titrimetric Determination of Thorium(IV) using 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic Acid as Titrant and SPADNS as an Indicator

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Thorium(IV) is determined by titrimetric method using DCTA as titrant and SPADNS as an indicator around pH 2.3-2.7 in a range of 48 $\mu\text{g}/10$ ml to 72.41 mg/25 ml with rsd as 1.6 to 0.44%. The optimum conditions like pH, concentration of DCTA and indicator, and temperature are established. The tolerance limits for foreign ions are determined. The method is useful for the determination of thorium in monazite.

DIRECT titrimetric methods for the determination of thorium(IV) using aminopolycarboxylic acids as titrant are not many. In almost all the earlier methods disodium salt of EDTA was used as titrant¹⁻³. Apart from EDTA, nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA)⁴, disodium salt of anthranilic-N,N-diacetic acid (ANDA)⁵, and N-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA)^{6,7} were also used for direct titration of thorium(IV) with some indicators. 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (DCTA) has been tried as a titrant using SPADNS as the indicator. The details of the method are given in this communication.

Experimental

Thorium(IV) solution: A 0.1 M stock solution of thorium nitrate, $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, A.R., (Fisons, Philadelphia, USA) was prepared with a few drops of nitric acid to prevent the hydrolysis of thorium and was standardized gravimetrically by the conventional benzoic acid method⁸.

DCTA solution: A 0.1 M stock solution of DCTA, AR (Merck, proanalysis) was prepared in distilled water with a few drops of sodium hydroxide to give a clear solution.

SPADNS solution: A 0.02% aqueous solution of SPADNS, (John Baker, Inc., Colorado, USA) was used.

All other solutions prepared were of A.R./G.R. quality reagents in distilled water.

Procedure:

The solution of thorium is diluted until it contains 2.41 to 72.41 mg metal per 25 ml solution. The pH is adjusted to 2.3-2.7 with dil. HNO_3 or NH_3 and 1.0 ml SPADNS solution is added. The solution is titrated with 0.01 M DCTA solution till the colour changed from blue violet to scarlet red. At lower concentrations of thorium i.e. 2.41 to 0.72 mg

per 25 ml and 0.72 mg to 48 μg per 10 ml, 0.002 and 0.001 M DCTA solution, respectively was used for titration.

One ml 0.01 M DCTA is equivalent to 2.321 mg thorium.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variation of pH: One ml 0.01 M solution of thorium was taken and diluted to 25 ml and the pH adjusted to different values between 1.5 to 3.5. It was found that the end point was sharp between pH 2.3 to 2.7. Below this pH range, the end point was not sharp and above this erratic values were obtained. Between pH 2.3 and 2.7, the results were accurate and reproducible. In all further experiments pH was maintained at 2.4.

Variation of DCTA: To estimate thorium at different levels of concentrations, suitable concentration of DCTA was used. (0.01 M for 72.41-2.41 mg Th per 25 ml, 0.002 M for 2.41-0.72 mg Th per 25 ml and 0.001 M for 0.72 mg-48 μg Th per 10 ml).

Effect of indicator variation: The amount of the indicator was varied from 0.5 ml to 1.5 ml (0.02% aq. soln.) and it was found that in all the cases the end point was sharp. However 1 ml indicator solution was used in further titrations. Below 0.5 ml, the end point was not distinct and erratic values were obtained.

Temperature study: The end point was sharp even at room temperature throughout the thorium concentration range, although upto 60° this could be detected easily.

Range, relative standard deviation: According to the procedure described, the optimum concentration of thorium that could be titrated was 0.048 mg Th per 10 ml to 72.41 mg Th per 25 ml. Below and above this range the end point was not sharp. Relative standard deviations of 16 samples in 2

different concentrations of thorium (0.048 mg/10 ml and 2.41 mg/25 ml) in the optimum range was 1.6% to 0.4, respectively.

Effect of foreign ions : The following ions (mg) do not give any significant error in the estimation of 2.41 mg of thorium in 25 ml according to the procedure described above: Hg(II) 300.00 (124.00 times); Ba(II) 280.00 (116 times); K(I) 200.00 (83 times); Sr(II) 200.00 (83 times); Ce(III) 90.00 (37 times); Mg(II) 75.00 (31 times); Mn(II) 70.00 (29 times); rare-earths 56.00 (23 times); U(VI) 55.00 (23 times); Zn(II) 50.00 (21 times); Ca(II) 25.00 (10 times); B(III) 18.12 (8 times); Pb(II) 15.00 (6 times); Co(II) 10.00 (4 times); Li(I) 10.00 (4 times); Cr(III) 8.00 (3 times); Al(III) 6.00 (2 times); Cd(II) 5.00 (2 times); Ni(II) 5.00 (2 times); Sn(II) 0.75; Fe(III) 0.03; Cu(II) 0.06; Zr(IV) 0.06; Ag(I) 0.00001; Ti(IV) 0.00004. Among the anions SO_4^{2-} 1.08; PO_4^{3-} 0.05; tartrate 0.26; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ 0.13; CH_3COO^- 21.8; F^- 0.02 do not interfere. However, at higher concentration the interference is observed for SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, F^- and tartrate.

Thorium(IV) forms a violet coloured complex with SPADNS at pH 2.3-3.0 and by titration with DCTA at pH 2.4 this violet colour is changed to scarlet red. This reaction has been utilised for direct titrimetric determination of very low concentration of thorium(IV) (48.0 $\mu\text{g}/10$ ml) using SPADNS as indicator. Since the titration is carried out in an acidic solution comparatively few cations form complexes with DCTA of sufficient strength to interfere. Thorium can be estimated in presence of the above mentioned foreign ions. The method finds use in the determination of thorium in monazite after the separation of thorium and lanthanides from the rest of the elements⁹ (Table 1).

1.95 g monazite after decomposition with conc. sulphuric acid was dissolved in ice-cold water, saturated with H_2S , filtered, H_2S boiled off and made upto 250 ml. From 100 ml of this solution thorium and rare-earths were precipitated with 10% oxalic acid, filtered, precipitate ignited in a platinum crucible, dissolved in conc. HCl and made upto 100 ml and used for titrations.

TABLE 1—MONAZITE ANALYSIS

EDTA titration ^{10*}						
Sl. No.	Monazite sample soln. (ml)	Dilution (ml)	pH	Indicator (drops)	EDTA PCV (ml)	Estimated Th (mg)
1.	6.0	25	3.0	3	1.80	4.178
2.	8.0	25	3.0	3	2.40	5.570
3.	10.0	25	3.0	3	3.00	6.963
DCTA titration						
Sl. No.	Monazite sample soln. (ml)	Dilution (ml)	pH	Indicator SPADNS (ml)	EDTA 0.01 M (ml)	Estimated Th (mg)
1.	6.0	25	2.4	1.0	1.80	4.178
2.	8.0	25	2.4	1.0	2.40	5.570
3.	10.0	25	2.4	1.0	3.00	6.963

*For comparison purpose thorium in monazite was also estimated by EDTA-PCV method and the results are given in Table 1.

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